

EFFECTIVENESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION IN THE PRIMARY GRADES

BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA ONA TILI TA'LIMINING SAMARADORLIGI

Xilolaxon Isaqova

FarDu Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar kafedrasi o'qituvchisi

Azizbek Vosiljonov

FarDu Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar kafedrasi o'qituvchisi

Annotation: this article is the native language used in interactive methods, the lesson in primary school, the subject that develops didactic games are given information about

Keywords: didactic o'the yin, will compete topqirlar, interactive methods are fast top.

The application of new forms of learning the native language primary school in the lesson, to test it in practice plays an important role. The reader through the native language classes skills and independent work. The development of the native language in the lesson, first of all, disclaimer of dogmatik methods of teaching, the more the reader to think, growing, thinking, encourage creative activity to show the application of techniques that native language skills and capabilities to work with the whole look through the nurturing of action that develops implements.

Education in mother tongue to the children of the thought of the business expansion, free thinking, to get to understand the mind of my neighbor, to get their opinions and describe orally and in writing, to the development of skills and qualifications to be in free communication with members of the community served. School practice, teachers of the creative team of teaching experience to the level of the requirements of the job today, "old" methods (disclaimer, it is "new" at the expense of filling on the basis of methods, but the methods of

teaching creative approach, using the integration capabilities to their internal work to put the entire educational program that shows the need to be carried out on the basis of improvement.

Growing didactic educational games that are created from the native language, looking to show creative activity to teach students: to determine the essence of the phenomenon of language, judgment and conclusions to motivate. Each of the educational games to demonstrate to the reader himself, to protect his views, the commission and ecstasy – it allows you to enjoy complete with. Each person needed in nurturing positive qualities: efficiency, acumen, topqirlik, alertness, determination, bilimdonlik, independence, entrepreneurship, creativity often as find content by educational games.

In the same game, just lessons — assignments to remain limited, despite the fact that ijodiylik but more motivating game – comes on strengthening attention to the instructions. After all, to thinking readers, to think, to create the text we do not teach the present time to put the lessons of the important requirements for the development of the person will not be achieved.

1.“Top fast” game. The teacher tells the students samples from people saying. Students understand, while I give many comments by students and teachers who are encouraging.saying such a line will continue. Sanoq on the meaning of the proverb and this will determine the number of of them are working. The number of the proverb, which includes a specified amount of deliver their meaning will be interpreted.

Example: “neighborhood parents to a child seven”, “eight Sanamay”, “a year of mulberry plant guy, gavhar dials a hundred years”, “a kalla — kalla, kalla two gold”...

Spelling in order to increase literacy readers, “wrote the right winner if good science and tolib if” game – use assignments is possible. In this game the teacher write on the board a certain number of them with a number of takes to

write according to the rules of spelling. For example, 1-2, 3-4, 5, 10, 15, 40, 55, 60, 70-80 units, 90, 100, v. h.

The number of students writing the words with numbers represented by the winner of the game may be won on the interaction based on the condition.

One of the unconventional shape and 2 of the lesson. “Topqirlar will compete in” the lesson. First graders are divided into two groups for the organization of this lesson. The theme of the groups studied within the framework of 3-4 pre-questions and assignments were made. Of governors of the latest knowledge levels of primary school, given the direct guidance of the teacher structure this assignment please. The bout the second group to the first group and second group in the first group gives questions and assignments. The teacher points to each group announced the analysis of returning and answers. The group who collect many points is considered the winner of the game.

“Will compete Topqirlar” of the lesson can be held in different forms,” for example, “journey to the world of Words”, “journey to the world”, “overcoming obstacles” I am v. h. like.

3. “Comment signs” game. In the game students are divided into three groups. 1-group of the melon color — shades of the 2-form, while the group - size, 3-group, his most favorite flavors — taste qualities denoting find.

1-group: blue, white, yellow, beige

2 groups: big, small, long, round.

3-group: Sweet, tasty, nutritious

While putting a photo of twisted melon teachers boards, 1–most favorite flavors from the group – representing taste, 2 color from the group shades, the 3–form from the group delivers to identify the quality of denoting size. Students write out all the words into the same slots game is considered the winner.

4. “What a good-yu, what's bad” game. Good and bad in this game the students determine the characteristics according to the requirements of their peers, and how the students are well-mannered, to say that they were students how

obscene is presented. Example: xususiyatlar good–smart, well-mannered, receptive, shirinsuxan , polite, educated, knowledgeable, wise, humble, ingenious. Bad features: irrational, beodob, a liar, aldoqchi, lazy, idle, ishyoqmas, berahm.

5.“Select the pairs” game. Teacher quality is the first part of a pair in this game that will tell the students to write both while his notebook part will go. Given the quality of the game on a pair of students wrote the winner will be considered. Example: trivia, good — bad, low – high, long close, sweet — bitter, white-black, v. h.

6.“How we will put the number” game. A combination of the number of words in this game is presented and the location of the point in the specified time to fill it with a group of students who has completed the winners will be listed. Recommended a combination of words : reader, school..., ... tree, ... room, ... tram, street..., ... flour, alfalfa, soil.... Example: reader 3, 1-school tree 4 units, 12 –room, 11-tram, 7 - street, a flour tin, a garden, a handful of alfalfa soil.

7.“Top put the correct answer to the question” game. Uzbekistan, which with neighboring countries? Do you know the name of the city in uzbekistan, of which?, How products are manufactured in uzbekistan?, The fruits of uzbekistan to the world, which gave the correct answer to the question of the famous students who will be the winner of the contest.

During the lesson the teacher “in their village (City) name description will cast could get?” the in — game using the instructions from the you can work on the spelling of outstanding horses. To do this, the teacher and students will do the task this topic before the father – father, grandfather – momolaringdan “your own village if you are in (your city)” the history of let's gather information about that is presented.

8.“In the yard and in the woods” game. O'qivchilarga the teacher gives comments about the game: the pets that live in the forest and the wild animals that live in the yard and think about them in two separate stake to get out of writing is called. Students they will write:

In the forest: in the yard: fox bear cow sheep goat horse lion wolf Which many animals a group of pupils or pupils write the name of the game at the specified time is considered the winner. The effectiveness of education depends on the degree the development of thinking in many ways. “Thought – Davletshin psychologist noted that t. m., person of high mental activity is a form of indirect and umumlashgan intiqom the real asset, the asset items and the connection between events and their relationship to the overall texture is the process of resonance”. So , if you go out the organization of the different games in each lesson , the lesson to the readers it increases interest in the subject in mind is saved.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshodbek o‘g‘li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o‘g‘li, V. A. (2022). XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 39-47.
2. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O‘RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 176-182.
3. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
4. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
5. Ботирова, Н. (2020). Обучающие возможности тестовых технологий. *Профессиональное образование и общество*, (3), 68-71.
6. Ботирова, Н. Д. (2019). Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (61), 4-6.
7. Ботирова, Н. Д. Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников development of productive thinking of younger schoolboys.

Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на, 4.

8. Ботирова, Н. Д., & Алимджонова, М. Ю. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИ ЭВРИСТИК ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ ОМИЛЛАРИ. Scientific progress, 3(4), 519-524.

9. Botirova Nasiba Djurabayevna INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS . Eastern European Scientific Journal Germany. 128 – 132 p. <http://www.auris-verlag.de>

10. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 914-917.

11. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 1040-1044.

12. Alimjanova, M. (2021). ABOUT GENDER STEREOTYPES. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 2(06), 72-76.

13. Janabergenova, A. J. (2018). Organization and Forms of Students' Independent Work on Higher Mathematics at Pedagogical University. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (2).

14. Janabergenova, A. J. (2021). Setting Goals on Smart Techniques and Affecting Student Motivation. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 9333-9336.

15. Askarova, D. (2022). FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1039-1044.

16. Askarova, D. I. (2022). The Role Of Folk Pedagogy In The Development Of Creativity Of Students Of Higher Educational Institutions. Oriental Journal of Social Sciences, 2(02), 89-96.

17. Dilafruz, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Va Oilada Gender Xususiyatlarni Shakllantirish Omillari. *Innovation In The Modern Education System*, 2(18), 183-189.
18. Askarova, D. I. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(10), 92-97.
19. Askarova, D. I., & Jabborova, M. K. (2022). The Introduction Of Gender Issues In Preschool Education On The Example Of Folk Pedagogy. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(05), 81-87.
20. Jabborova, M. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 129-132.
21. Jabborova, M. (2022). BO'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNI TAYYORLASH TIZIMIDA MALAKAVIY AMALIYOTNING ROLI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 167-173.
22. Kodiraliyevna, J. M. (2022). TARBIYACHI KASBINING MA'NAVIY AXLOQIY NEGIZLARI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 2), 64-70.
23. Zhabborova, M. R. K. (2021). Мактабгача таълим соҳаси талабаларида бошқарувчанлик қобилиятларини ривожлантириш. *Молодой ученый*, (17), 394-395.
24. Dilafruz, Y., Marifatxon, J., Rasuljonovna, E. Z., & Muqaddasxon, M. (2022). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMGA YANGICHA YONDASHUV. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 3), 121-125.
25. E. Najmiddinov, A. Rasujonov, & J. Rahimov (2022). FARG'ONA VODIYSI SUV HAVZALARIDAGI BALIQLAR GELMINTLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 145-151. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335759

26. Najmiddinov, Eldor , Rasuljonov, Adhamjon, & Rahimov, Javohir (2022). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10), 1049-1054.
27. E. Najmiddinov (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА “ИХТИОЛОГИЯ ВА ГИДРОБИОЛОГИЯ” СОҲАЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 152-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335800
28. E. Najmiddinov (2022). TABIATNING MAKTABGACHA TA’LIM YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI BARKAMOL AVLOD BO’LIB SHAKLLANISHIDAGI ANAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B8), 149-154. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336353
29. Юлдашев, Э., & Нажмиддинов, Э. (2013). БРАКОНИДЫ (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) РОДА ROGAS NEES ФАУНЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In *Биоразнообразие и рациональное использование природных ресурсов* (pp. 134-136).
30. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., Кучбоев, А. Э., Мухаммадиев, М. А., & Соатов, Б. Б. (2021). Эколого-морфологические характеристики нематод рода *Rhabdochona*-паразитов обыкновенной маринки. *Теория и практика борьбы с паразитарными болезнями*, (22), 387-393.
31. Kuchboev, A. E., Najmidinov, E. K., Mukhamediev, M. A., Karimova, R. R., & Yildiz, K. (2021). Morphological and ecological features of some nematodes of the genus *Rhabdochona* in marinka obtained from Fergana Valley, Uzbekistan. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 45(4), 1084-1089.
32. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 326-329.

33. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 74-76.
34. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
35. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
37. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.
38. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.

39. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 235-239.
40. Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING AQLIY TARAQQIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHIDA O'YIN RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI FAOLIYAT SIFATIDA. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207–209.
41. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.
42. To'lqinovna, Y. D. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA МАТЕМАТИК ТАСАВВУРЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ МЕТОДЛАРИ. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
43. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To'lqinovna (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA БАДИЙ ТАСВИРЛАР ОРҚАЛИ ИЗЧИЛ НУТҚНИ РИВОJЛАНТИРИШ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
44. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE

ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.

45. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
46. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG'LOM BO'LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 80-88.
47. SultonaliMannopov, A., AbdusalomSoliev, U., & TokhirShokirov, R. (2021). Development of Uzbek National Singing Art during Independence. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 6845-6853.
48. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). МИЛЛИЙ МУСИҚА МАДАНИЯТИ ВА УНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ (фольклор, дostonчилик, мақом мисолида). *Science and innovation*, 1(С3), 31-38.
49. Shakirov, T. N. (2022). SUCCESSION IS THE MAIN PRINCIPLE OF DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL MUSIC CULTURE. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(06), 1-10.
50. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). АБУ НАСР ФОРОВИЙНИНГ МУСИҚА ИЛМИГА ҚЎШГАН ХИССАСИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 353-359.
51. Nurmamatovich, S. T. (2021). Theoretical of national music culture fundamentals.
52. Qizi, G. S., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). The use of anthroponyms and pseudonyms in alisher Navoi's gazelles. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 349-353.

53. Tillaboyeva, G., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA BADIY TAXALLUSLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI. *Студенческий вестник*, (13-5), 70-72.
54. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). ALISHER NAVOIY SHE’RIYATIDA “SHAXS” TUSHUNCHASI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 182-196.
55. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA LIBOS NOMLARI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 506-514.
56. Mohinur, D., & Rahimjon, U. (2022). A Study Of Memory Processes And Their Development In Preschool. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 62-65.
57. Rahim, U. (2021, May). SOCIAL FACTORS OF THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 6-7).
58. Usmonov, R. (2022). O‘SMIRLAR XULQIDA NAMOIYISHKORLIK G‘AYRATLILIK XUSUSIYATLARI TADQIQ ETISH METODOLOGIYASI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 127-135.
59. Usmonov, R. (2022). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRI SHAXSIGA XOS ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDOSHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 120-126.
60. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOIYISHKORLIK, G‘AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO‘LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
61. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOIYISHKORLIK, G‘AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON

BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.

62. Rakhmonovich, U. R. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 820-824.
63. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
64. Қурбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
65. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
66. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). О 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
67. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI O 'SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMMOSINI O 'RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.
68. Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA

TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.

69. Dilshodbek O'g'li, R. S. (2022). The Role Of Physical Culture In Providing The Psychological Health Of The Athlete. *Innovative Developments And Research In Education, Canada*.

70. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH–IJTIMOIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 66-70.

71. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 215-221.

72. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 256-259.